

INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. Intercultural communication is communication between representatives of different cultures. Effectiveness and success of intercultural communication occurs only when the communicators, who know different cultures and languages, understand that each of them is "different" and each of them, alternatively, "foreign" interlocutors. Acquaintance with the culture of other nations is one of the most important social tasks of translation and translator in the field of professional communication. This article talks about respecting the traditional values and customs of different countries, not trampling on their cultural heritage and preserving them for future generations, as well as learning foreign languages in order to ensure quality and efficiency in foreign language education.

Key words: representatives of culture, Intercultural communication, communicative space, human thinking, conflict situation, globalization process.

INTRODUCTION

The modern communicative space is a very complex system, one of the main places in which belongs to different types of communication. The reason for this is that a person behaves differently in different situations and circumstances, and therefore, in each case, he interacts with other people in a unique way. In addition, the nature and characteristics of communication are determined by means and methods of information transmission, subjects of communication, its goals and many other reasons. All this makes it possible to distinguish different types of communication. The distribution of certain types of communication in modern communication science is carried out for several reasons, so the number of communication types in different sources varies significantly. In addition, each type of communication has its own theoretical basis and expression. At the same time, the functional approach to this issue allows us to distinguish the following types of communication: transnational, business, social, international, interpersonal, mass, intercultural, etc. Of all the mentioned types of communication, intercultural communication is the first for us.

The objective basis of intercultural communication is the differences between cultures that develop during the formation of each ethnic culture. As mentioned above, people's life activities and relationships are determined by the norms that exist in a certain culture, they regulate almost all areas of human thinking and behavior and affect the nature of perception, evaluation and interpersonal relationships. . Education, upbringing, historical memory, traditions, customs and language develop a system of orientations that help people to successfully overcome everyday situations and various problems.

MAIN PART

The 21st century is marked by the beginning of a new stage of human development. It has become a stable process of globalization, which determines the most important directions

in the development of human society. As a result of this process, socio-economic, political and socio-cultural changes significantly changed the image of the modern world and affected the life activities of almost all people on earth. The expansion of various connections caused by globalization, the growth of tourism, the opportunity to study abroad, the exchange of ideas of different students, foreign practices and many other events and facts have made the problems of intercultural communication and cooperation more urgent.

It is the duty of each of us to respect the concepts and traditions of many peoples in our country, to treat them well, and not to trample on their cultural heritage and pass it on to the next generation. Another important aspect is professional knowledge and personnel who have achieved perfection in all fields, which is the goal of all higher education institutions. It is knowledge and skills, mastering foreign languages that can meet all the criteria of the present time. In particular, the inclusion of the principle of social solidarity in our new Constitution will help more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in Uzbekistan, regardless of their nationality, language, religion, gender, social origin, and position in society, on the way to building a new Uzbekistan. serves to further develop mutual cooperation. In this, intercultural communication allows participation in relationships at all levels. It is no exaggeration to say that the cultural unification of peoples is keeping pace with the times, while information technologies are rapidly developing in the 21st century. Only those personnel who are intelligent and diligently approach languages, who can exchange ideas with foreigners in every field, who are patriots, who are determined to protect and develop the interests of their country and compatriots with high knowledge and will, can find solutions to very important global issues and bring our nation to the world. can recognize. In Uzbekistan, the field of teaching foreign languages has become one of the priority directions of the state social policy. Relations between different confessions are based on mutual respect and tolerance. Religious and cultural tolerance means respecting each other's language, religion, lifestyle, customs and traditions, national-cultural heritage, valuing their honor, dignity, and honor of people of different nationalities. This ensures stability of religious and cultural tolerance and peace.

This process did not bypass our country either. Uzbeks are increasingly participating in international political and economic organizations, international events, activities of multinational companies, some students are studying abroad, and Uzbek tourists are traveling around the world. To successfully communicate with representatives of different countries, it is necessary to know not only the appropriate language, but also the rules of foreign culture: behavior, psychology, culture, history of other countries, and most importantly, to understand the mechanism of communication in order to avoid misunderstandings of representatives of other cultures need

Each person reacts to the outside world according to these characteristics of his culture. These cultural norms are often not recognized by the individual because they are part of his personality. Knowing the specifics of one's own culture comes into contact with people who control other cultural norms in their behavior. At the same time, such interaction often creates uncomfortable or conflicting situations and requires in-depth study.

The behavior of people belonging to other cultures is not unpredictable, it can be studied and predicted, but it requires special educational programs aimed at developing knowledge and skills of intercultural communication.

The characteristics of intercultural communication are studied at the interdisciplinary level and within such disciplines as cultural studies, psychology, linguistics, ethnology, anthropology, sociology, each of which uses its own approaches in its research. To begin with, the classic concept of culture to describe intercultural communication is conscious and unconscious. rules, norms, values, structures, artifacts - used as a more or less stable system of national or ethnic culture. As a scientific discipline, intercultural communication is in its initial stage and is distinguished by two characteristic features: practical nature (the goal is representatives of different cultures o Facilitating communication between people, reducing the potential for conflicts) and interdisciplinarity. However, to describe the processes of intercultural communication and understand its specific features, the framework model that we will use in the future is more suitable.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that intercultural communication is an integral part of human professional culture. The culture of business communication promotes effective cooperation between business partners. It is interesting that in many foreign countries such a scientific direction as "communication (communication) science" is developing. This scientific direction studies different types and forms of communication from the perspective of linguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, rhetoric, linguistics and cultural studies, etc. Studying this topic is a long and arduous process, everyday structures and relationships, both interpersonal and international, are in the process of change.

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